

Appendix A.

Inventory of Archaeological Sites: Key to Inventory Codes

The codes used in each column of the site inventory are defined in the following paragraphs.

GRID- The Grid number as listed here is arranged to group sites together by 10x10 km grid square. Thus the first site in the inventory, S-119, is in the grid square that is identified by the grid coordinates of the SW corner of the square, 58 north, 88 east. the site is located at 39 n., 27 e. within the square. The grid numbers must be rearranged as follows if you plan to use them with a program that will produce a map or calculate such data as distance to nearest neighbor; thus- Nn-Ee, that is 5838-8827.

Citation of the original publication, where known, is indicated according to the following codes, which appear as a prefix for either field numbers (FLD # A, FLD # B) or site names (NOTES):

- A- Alden 1979, Table 19
- B- Bergner 1937
- G- Gotch 1968, 1969, 1971
- H- Herzfeld 1935 and Tilia 1968:85, note
- J- Jacobs 1980, Table 5
- K- Kleiss 19xx
- R- Rosenberg 1988, pc field notes
- S- Sumner 1972, Appendix A and subsequent unpublished surveys.
Some late Sasanian and Islamic sites, classified by the late Andrew Williamson (pc), are shown on maps in Whitcomb 1977 and 1979.
- T- Tilia 1978, Figure 1
- V- Vanden Berghe 1952, 1954, 1959, 1968
- W- surveyed by the late Andrew Williamson, published in Sumner 1972, Whitcomb 1977, or first published here.

Site names reported by Vanden Berghe (1952, 1954, 1959, 1968) or Gotch (1968, 1969, 1971) are listed in the site inventory column where they can be identified with reasonable certainty; Citations are found in the site inventory notes column for a few sites that are not coded in the citation (C) column.

FLD # A- Field numbers assigned by Sumner (1972 Appendix A) and for additional unpublished sites added after 1971. Sumner field numbers for sites previously reported by Vanden Berghe have a V- prefix. Sumner field numbers are also listed for sites later resurveyed by Alden and Jacobs and for sites surveyed by Andrew Williamson (W-) at my request. The sherds from most of these collections are in the collection of the University of Pennsylvania Museum.

FLD # B- Field numbers used by Alden (1979, Table 19), Jacobs (1980 Table 5), and Rosenberg (pc) are indicated by a prefix: A-, J-, or R-. The correlation of field numbers shown in columns FLD # A and FLD # B is my interpretation, based on maps and aerial photographs not available to Alden and Jacobs at the time of their survey. In some cases these correspondences are not the same as those proposed by Alden and Jacobs. The grid numbers assigned to sites are also my interpretation and do not always correspond to the grid numbers assigned by Alden and Jacobs.

MOR- A classification of site morphology or type; up to 3 codes may be assigned.

- A- fire altar, as at Kuh-e Ayyub or Naqshi Rustam
- B- stone building ruins or isolated stone architectural elements
- C- complex mound; a cluster of small mounds, often, but not always Islamic
- D- dam or other irrigation work (not canal, cf code N)
- E- standing or ruined emamzadeh

- F- fort or citadel, usually on a mountain, ridge, or spur
- G- ghare, cave, rock shelter
- H- surface site, no recognizable mounding
- I- inscription
- J- quarry
- K- kharabi, a recently abandoned village with mud brick wall stubs still standing
- L- mounded habitation site on a natural hill, extent of mounding difficult to estimate
- M- abandoned water powered mill building, millstone, or oil press
- N- nahr, irrigation canal
- O- ostekan, rock carved niche
- P- pol, bridge
- Q- qale mound- These sites are an erosional stage following kharabi (code K); village or compound wall remains in the form of a low embankment, usually rectangular. Many low qale sites, up to 2 m ht., are Islamic; steep, tall qale sites are often Partho-Sasanian.
- R- rock relief, as at Naqshi Rostam
- S- rubble stone walls or tent stands (cf code B)
- T- tall, tell, tol, tepe, tappeh, mound
- V- abandoned caravanserai
- W- rock cut or freestanding tomb, as at Naqshi Rostam or Takhte Rostam
- X- exposure platform or trough
- Z- stone paved road

H- height, 0= less than 0.5 m, 1= 0.5-1.4, etc, up to 9= 8.5-9.4; the height of taller mounds is listed as rounded number.

ISL- The code P or a area estimate (ie. 1.0 = 1 ha) indicates an Islamic, Parthian, or Sasanian component. Details for these sites are listed in a separate inventory.

ACH-MSK- These column headings stand for the Kur River Basin chronological phases: ACH- Achaemenid, S-T- Shogha-Teimuran, QAL- Qaleh, KAF- Kaftari, BAN- Banesh, LAP- Lapui, BAK- Bakun, SHM- Shamsabad, JAR- Jari, MSK- Mushki.

These columns contain the estimated area assigned to each component. The largest number assigned to a component on a site is the total site area (ha) measured maximum length times maximum width. Earlier components are assigned either an average components area, which is 1.2 ha, or a basic component area, which is 0.8 ha, on the basis of the relative frequency of sherds of that component in the surface collection. There are two other codes used in these columns:

D- A component of this phase may be present but the typological status of sherds or other dating criteria is not certain.

S- This component is not counted as a regular habitation component; Code S is assigned when a terminal or next to terminal component is represented by only 1 or 2 sherds or only by restorable or whole pots that are assumed to be from a burial. Special (code S) components are assumed to be a special use of the site as a cemetery, as a briefly occupied camp site, or for some other special function.

Note- Additional information: Site names, presence of Asupas ware; BR- presence of Bakun coarse red ware, Kiln- evidence of ceramic production, evidence of unreported excavations, evidence of burials

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	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	NORTH	EAST	FLD # A	MOR	AREA	HT	3	2	1	S	FNN#	NAME (P66)
237	6071	8474										Kushk Hezar
238	6072	8473										7 Hezar Shaikh
239	6073	8461										5 Kushk?
240	6081	8464	S-5K0	QT	0.5					S		
241	6087	8458										Aliabad
242	6088	8432										8 Jari
243	6090	8433	S-5W5	Q	1.0							
244	6097	8491	S-5X0	Q	1.0	1						
245	6097	8493	S-5W9	T	0.3	2	3					
246	6005	8555	S-563	Q			3	2				
247	6015	8549										Asef abandoned caravansera
248	6015	8553	S-564	QT	6.6	1	3	2				
249	6016	8549	A-10H3-I	T	0.1	1						
250	6017	8551	A-10H2-I	T	0.3	2						
251	6019	8549	S-564C	T	1.1	3	3					
252	6024	8511	A-10G2-I	H	0.2							
253	6033	8512	A-10G3-I	H	0.3							
254	6035	8518	A-10G1-I	C	6.4	4						
255	6036	8508										4 Shaikhabud
256	6037	8536	S-565	T	0.6	2						
257	6050	8530	S-5R6	QC	2.9	2			1			
258	6071	8582										44 Gondashlu, Olya (Kuse or J)
259	6076	8502	M	C	50.0	3						
260	6080	8564	S-5P2	H	1.0							
261	6087	8552	S-5P1	QF	0.2							
262	6090	8598	S-5Q1	T	0.3							
263	6093	8590	S-5Q2	Q	0.4							
264	6095	8554	S-5Q5	QQC	1.0							
265	6099	8556										• Gowd Zereshk, RJ
266	6024	8685	S-500	T	4.2	4	2					
267	6025	8689	S-501	T	1.5	1	2					
268	6053	8630	S-5P5	T	1.0							
269	6054	8665	S-527	QT	0.1							
270	6055	8668										• Ozun Darreh
271	6060	8660										45 Gondashlu, Sofia (Sar Ches
272	6062	8652	S-528	Q	0.2							
273	6072	8640										• Maragalu
274	6075	8630	S-529	Q	0.2							
275	6076	8618	S-5P8	Q	0.3							
276	6077	8689	S-6A0	T	2.5	1						
277	6089	8603	S-5Q0	T	0.4							
278	6010	8781	S-	S	3.0							
279	6010	8799	S-361	Q	0.8	1						
280	6012	8786	S-368	T	0.5							
281	6013	8771	S-3A9	T	0.3	1						
282	6013	8776	S-308	T	1.3	3	3	2				
283	6014	8785	V-367	Q	0.5		2	1				

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L
1	NORTH	EAST	FLD # A	MOR	AREA	HT	3	2	1	S	FNN#	NAME (P66)
566	6219	8310	S-BZE	T	0.1							
567	6220	8337										Ebrahimabad
568	6220	8374									20	Kheyraabad, BZ
569	6221	8303									55	Poshte Bagh
570	6222	8633	S-BAZ	T	0.4					S		
571	6223	8355										Sesnion
572	6224	8379	S-	T	0.6	1						
573	6225	8359	S	TT	1.0							
574	6225	8378										Gavamabad
575	6231	8385									•	Beheshtabad, BZ
576	6233	8337									18	Reijan
577	6234	8354	S-5505	Q	0.8							
578	6234	8358	S-5506	C	2.3							
579	6236	8389	S-BAJ	T	0.1							
580	6237	8337	S-5502	C	2.0	5						
581	6240	8305	S-5U8	Q	0.3							
582	6240	8341										Marjanak
583	6243	8357										Ziadabad
584	6242	8387									21	Boserjan, BZ (Baserjan, B)
585	6248	8339	S-5503	C								
586	6250	8365									237	Gharovan (abandoned now)
587	6253	8335	S-BZH	Q								
588	6254	8334									24	Haft Khan
589	6254	8376									•	Hajiabad, BZ
590	6260	8337	S-5504	C								
591	6261	8370	S-5T4	QT	2.2	1						
592	6261	8386	S	Q								
593	6264	8394	S-5T5	QT								
594	6267	8353										Falak
595	6271	8307	S	M								
596	6272	8365										Hasanabad
597	6275	8346									26	Sagvan
598	6277	8340										Kushk Mohammad
599	6277	8343	S-5U3	QQ								
600	6279	8374										Qabaieh
601	6280	8344	S-5U1	Q			3					
602	6280	8373	S-5T0	QT								
603	6281	8318									25	Doshman Ziyari
604	6282	8369	S-5T2	T								
605	6282	8375										Haftjan